

POST-BUCKLING AND MEMBRANE STRUCTURAL CAPABILITY OF COMPOSITE SHELL STRUCTURES

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Aluminum shell structures exploit post-buckling and membrane strength to achieve minimum weight. The application of fibrous composites to these structures offers significant weight savings, provided post-buckling and membrane deformations can also be permitted.

This paper discusses the physics involved in shear and compression post-buckling and membrane pressure pillowing, and compares their forced displacement forms. First level, simplified mathematical treatise are presented. The more complex rigorous mathematics are avoided, emphasis being placed on the qualitative aspects. The objective is to contribute to a fundamental understanding of post-buckling behavior which will help establish practical design limits.

It is shown that the interlaminar and substructure separation forces can be assessed, with reasonable accuracy, once the displacement shapes are established.

INTRODUCTION

The use of composites has more recently been explored for applications other than wing and empennage torsion boxes. In these structures, particularly fuselage shells, a lower load intensity range is encountered. In the past these shell structures have generally been fabricated from aluminum alloy sheet supported by formed frames and stiffeners with the skin thicknesses ranging from 0.60 to 2 millimeters. Examples of these types of structures are shown in figure 1.

In applying fibrous composites to these structures, a nonbuckling criterion would result in configuration optimizations different from those which would be selected if post-buckling were allowed. Devices for increasing effective skin thicknesses, such as various forms of sandwich construction, would be favored over monolithic construction. It is, therefore, necessary to establish allowables for post buckling of monolithic composite panels.

Figure 1 - Typical airframe shell structure

RELATED ALUMINUM EXPERIENCE

There is a tendency to emphasize the differences between metallic and composite structures rather than their similarities. There is a distinct similarity in the behavior of shell structures. It is, therefore, worthwhile to review the ground rules applied to aluminum shell structures.

Post-buckling in aluminum shell structures was generally limited by one of the following.

- No shear buckling below a given fraction of ultimate load

$$\frac{q_{ult}}{q_{cr}} < 5.0 \text{ (to minimize fatigue)}$$

- Aerodynamic surface smoothness
- Aesthetic - (no pillowing or buckling in the static ground loading)
- Aeroelastic stiffness requirements
- Acoustic fatigue and noise transmissibility
- Service handling and damage

The limits established were somewhat arbitrary. In some aircraft buckling was allowed below the lg level flight loads. Some aircraft clearly showed buckles just sitting on the ground.

Shear and compression panel tests of representative structures were conducted to finalize the design. Proof tests on the complete structures (fuselages, wings, tails, etc.) were conducted prior to first flight and the appropriate modifications made. There was no concern about skin delamination because the shear and transverse properties relative to the longitudinal strength were high. The differences in this respect between the interlaminar properties of graphite-epoxy composites and solid metal sheet are shown in table 1.

TABLE 1. SHEAR AND TRANSVERSE PROPERTIES COMPARISON

MATERIAL	STRENGTH - MPa (ksi)			STRENGTH RATIO	
	LONGITUDINAL TENSION	(INTER-LAMINAR) SHEAR	(INTERLAMINAR) TRANSVERSE TENSION	SHEAR LONGITUDINAL	TRANSVERSE TENSION LONGITUDINAL TENSION
ALUMINUM SHEET	448(65)	276(40)	448(65)	0.62	1.0
Gr/E QUASI ISOTROPIC	621(90)	31(4.5)	41(6.0)	0.05	0.07

The allowable post-buckling level was usually established by a local mechanical attachment failure or stiffener column-crippling. Failures usually occurred at intersection areas of panel support structure.

The basic data available for initial sizing came from many sources. Stress Memo Manuals, Data sheets, and NACA reports typified by NACA TN 2661. [Reference 1.] Curves for initial buckling in terms of panel length to width (a/b) and panel width to thickness (b/t) had common usage. Post-buckling and/or crippling allowable prediction methodology varied from company to company, and for the most part was semi-empirical in nature with constants introduced to fit the test data bank. Static strength was the prime issue, fatigue rarely entered the picture except as a general judgment factor.

COMPOSITE FATIGUE CONSIDERATIONS

Durability requirements for nonbuckled structures have been covered in a general way by limiting the gross area strain at ultimate load. This is similar to the approach used in aluminum structures. In these structures, an ultimate load gross area stress cutoff is established, which is consistent with the fatigue quality which can be achieved in the numerous structural details. Ultimate load strain cutoff is a candidate for establishing post-buckling and membrane limits for composite panels. This is in line with past practice and could provide a practical basis for design.

A generally held view is that we do not have the same tension-tension fatigue problem in G_r/E composites as we have in aluminum structures. This view is based primarily on thick sheet nonbuckled test specimen experience and is not necessarily applicable to thin sheet post-buckled shells. It is expected that matrix initiated failures will establish fatigue life for thin sheet. A review of some of the compressive and tensile potential loadings and orientations which could induce matrix crack initiation and propagation are presented in figure 2.

The forced displacements which may induce matrix cracking and stiffener peeling are shown in figure 3. Compression, shear, and pressure pillowing are illustrated. An angular sweep as represented by " θ " in figure 3 shows the existence of combined bending and direct strains for compression and tension existing over a wide range of azimuth positions. It seems logical, therefore, to assume for a worst case assessment that the most critical surface fiber orientation exists irrespective of the actual stacking sequence. For evaluation purposes the case 1 (figure 3) matrix cracking mode will be considered for tension-tension and combinations of case 1 and case 5 will be considered for compression-compression and compression-tension loadings.

BASIC COMPOSITE MATERIAL FATIGUE DATA

A review of the many existing reports on fatigue tests does not yield definitive data for thin laminates. The myriad combinations of fibers, matrices, stacking sequences, fiber volume, and quality levels limits meaningful comparisons between data, particularly where strain levels, or properties to convert to strain levels, are not quantified. It is difficult to establish the equivalent of the crack initiation fatigue life used in metallics. Most of the composite fatigue data is for thick sheets often with holes. Application to thin sheets of the level of one millimeter (0.040 in.) thick is at best intuitive. The various failure function hypotheses are given in [reference 2]. Strain is shown to be a more sensitive parameter than stress in establishing allowables. Strain is also the basis of forced displacement shape.

A review of the fatigue data might suggest a matrix cracking tension-tension strain versus life curve of the form shown in figure 4. Similar curves in terms of strain might be evolved for compression-compression and tension-compression. The tension-tension curve for matrix crack initiation is also suggested from the results of repeated torsion loads applied to a $\pm 45^\circ$ fiber orientation tube [reference 3]. While the results of these tests are given in shear strain an equivalent tensile strain across the fibers can be determined. Future fatigue tests on thin sheet panels should help establish failure modes and should point the way to a design allowable data format.

ANALYSIS

A simple strip theory approach is suggested for a post-buckling evaluation. An example of this procedure as applied to panel compression is shown in figure 5. The limits of this analysis particularly for anisotropic plates is recognized. It is an analyses tool which requires engineering judgment. Post-buckling, however, is a result of a forced displacement and a smooth deflected form has to be established almost independent of the sheet elastic properties.

CASE	ILLUSTRATION	DESCRIPTION
1		TENSION STRAIN ACROSS FIBERS ON SURFACE
2		TENSION STRAIN ACROSS FIBERS BELOW SURFACE
3		TENSION AND SHEAR STRAIN ACROSS SURFACE FIBERS (QUASI ISOTROPIC)
4		SHEAR TRANSFER LOADING FIBER TO FIBER
5		INDUCED TENSION LOAD NON STRAIGHT FIBER IN COMPRESSION
6		PEEL OFF FROM STIFFENER
7		INDUCED SHEAR FROM PANEL DEFORMATION

Figure 2 - Matrix dominated crack initiation modes.

Figure 3 - Fuselage - forced displacement.

Figure 4 - Expected form of strain vs life curve.

The edge member represented by the stringer or longeron is assumed to remain stable up to a given ultimate strain value. After initial panel buckling, the center panel no longer deforms under direct compression and continued forced strain is compensated for by increasing the depth of the buckles in the panel. The forced displacement shape at the center of the panel can be represented by a sine curve and the displacement magnitude can be expressed in terms of the post-buckled strain as shown in figure 5. The following conclusions can be drawn from the strip analysis.

- The maximum deflection of the half wave is a direct function of the wave length and the square root of the edge member strain after panel initial buckling.
- The deflection to wave length ratio remains constant at a given post-buckled strain.
- Induced bending surface strain in the compression strip is proportional to the thickness of the panel.

Analyses of the induced strains normal to the loading is somewhat more complex and very much dependent on the surrounding restraints. A strip representation which includes stiffener attachment peeling forces is shown in figure 6. The analyses assumes a complete lateral restraint of the panel in the local buckled area. Tension strains calculated using this simplified analysis would represent the upper limit of the strains which could be realized. The lateral restraint on a compression test panel depends on the fixture, edge member stiffness and the stiffness of the cross members on the panel.

The induced lateral membrane force causes a sharpening of the radius of curvature at the stiffener which is dependent on the level of stiffener restraint.

Figure 5 - Strip representation compressive displacement

Figure 6 - Strip analysis tension strain.

Application of the strip analysis to an idealized 152 mm (6 in.) wide compression panel yields the compression surface strains versus applied strains shown in figure 7. To highlight the effect of width to thickness ratio (b/t) four thicknesses are shown. The induced lateral tensions at the sharp radius location near the stringer are shown in figure 8 for two thicknesses. The tensile strains are high because of the assumption of complete lateral restraint. The actual restraint in a panel or structure would be considerably less. Each case requires evaluation.

Figure 7 - Panel longitudinal compressive strain

Figure 8 - Panel lateral tensile strain at edge of stiffener.

COMPRESSION PANEL TEST RESULTS

In 1976 at Lockheed a compression panel of the dimensions shown in figure 9 was tested to destruction. The object was to verify by test the stability of a typical T300/5209 graphite-epoxy hat stiffened panel containing three stiffeners and a single rib attachment. Shadow moiré techniques were employed to define the buckle wave forms and strain gauges were used to measure the panel response to compressive loading. A schematic diagram of the shadow moiré test arrangement is given in figure 9. A photo of the pattern near failure load is given in figure 10. Out of plane panel skin surface displacements derived from the patterns are given in figure 11. Displacements calculated using the strip analysis and the measured values are compared. Failure occurred at the 0.004 strain level. An analysis assessment of surface strains and peeling indicates failure could be expected at this level.

Figure-9 - Shadow moiré test arrangement.

Figure 10 - Moiré fringe patterns depicting buckling near failure - 415,000 N (93.3 kips) load.

Analysis: Eff length = 119 mm (4.7 in.) Buckling strain: $e_{cr} = .0025$
 Strain: $e_x - e_{cr} = .0015$ Failure strain: $e_x = .004$
 $\delta = 3 \text{ mm (0.12 in.)}$

Figure 11 - Out-of-plane skin surface displacements at an axial compression load of 415000 N (93.34 Kips) - T300/5209 graphite-epoxy hat stiffened panel.

SHEAR POST-BUCKLING

Under independent research a program was initiated at Lockheed to determine the post buckling behavior of thin G_r/E sheet composite panels in shear. The program had the following objectives.

- Determine the post-buckling behavior of thin sheet composite panels in shear up to ultimate strength.
- Determine the fatigue capability of panels subject to repetitive buckling.

One 8 ply one millimeter (0.040 in.) T300/5208 graphite-epoxy shear panel and one 12 ply panel were statically tested to ultimate. One 8 ply panel was fatigue cycled in shear under a random fatigue spectrum representing three lifetimes (based on a fuselage side panel loading). After this test, no damage was detected.

Shadow moiré techniques were used to define the skin buckling wave form to static ultimate load. The extent of panel skin buckling at a shear flow of 153 N/mm (874 lb/in) is shown in figure 12. The moiré pattern after panel failure 157 N/mm (899 lb/in shear flow) is shown in figure 13. A view of the failed static shear panel with the shadow moiré grille screen removed is shown in figure 14. The maximum out-of-plane skin surface displacements for the center bay were determined from the moiré fringe and are shown in figure 15. For analysis comparison the wave should be plotted against the buckle minimum and maximum axes.

Application of the strip analysis technique to shear post-buckling is shown in figure 16. A comparison between the deflection and strain determined from the analysis and the 8 ply shear panel test results are shown in figure 17. Typical strain gauge results for the 12 ply panel along with analysis values are shown in figure 18.

Figure 12 - Moiré fringes depicting skin buckling at a shear flow of 153 N/mm (874 lb/in) in static test panel.

Figure 13 - Moiré fringes after panel failure.

Figure 14 - Stiffener side of panel after failure.

FATIGUE RESULTS

The fatigue spectrum applied to the 8 ply panel is shown in figure 19. Panel tensile strains versus applied cycles are presented. Also shown is a tangent theory summation which is compared with the strain - N curve suggested in figure 4.

Figure 15 - Maximum out-of-plane panel skin surface displacements - center bay - T300/5208 graphite-epoxy shear panel.

Figure 16 - Shear analysis.

STRESS RANGE

The effects of stress range (R) are shown in figure 20. Of particular interest is shear reversal which switches the structure carrying tension to compression buckling and vice versa.

Figure 17 - Analysis test results comparison.

FIBER ORIENTATION

The fiber orientations to give high initial buckling values and those which would favor post-buckling durability are not necessarily compatible.

PRESSURE PILLOWING

Pressure pillowing is yet another example of forced displacement. The displacement form is shown in figure 3. The deformation condition is created as follows.

- Fuselage expands under pressure loading.
- Expansion is restrained by frames and stiffeners.

Figure 20 - Effects of stress range.

- A differential forced displacement between frames and skin is created which results in fixation at the frames.
- Bending and direct strains are created in the panels from the following action.

An assessment of the strains induced in the surface can be obtained using the strip analysis approach shown for compression and shear.

CONCLUSIONS

From the limited test results and the first level simplified analysis assessment the following conclusions are drawn.

A post-buckling static capability in compression and shear for flat panels has been demonstrated.

A post-buckling repeated loading capability in shear for flat panels has been demonstrated.

Induced bending membrane displacement can be assessed with simple strip analysis and the induced surface strains provide a basis for strength assessments.

High induced strains and peeling forces can exist at the stiffeners and are amenable to analysis assessment provided edge restraints are evaluated.

The strains induced by forced displacement are a function of the thickness of the panels.

REFERENCES

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- 3 FUJEZAK, R.R., Torsional Fatigue Behavior of Graphite-Epoxy Cylinders, AIAA presentation.